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DATA CENTRIC APPROACH LEADING TO SERVICE EXCELLENCE IN CRESCENT POWER

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Abstract:

A stable & beneficial industrial process system, enriched with customizable features and quality always required a flexible business model.

Keeping the safety aspect in mind and considering the default behavior of the process in classical, imperative form and later transforming it to a declarative, data centric process model is the preliminary objective of such system and the secondary system obtained is the input of preliminary consideration which provides a simple human understandable process model.

The importance of data flow to make a successful process can be achieved by legitimate planning and arranging process information for getting an end product is the part of overarching business. The transformed model will be in compliance to the existing complex system norms in a dispersed & heterogenic form.

In this paper, I will discuss the data centric approach to monitor and control the complex, manual and irrational work & power flow process for achieving better service by creating excellence through integrated process system (IPS)& 7th block megawatt (MW) low/high reversal system (concept of pre power scheduling technique).

Index Terms -Data centric, Legitimate, Process data, Complex system, IPS, MW reversal system

Introduction

In this work two different unique techniques have been proposed which not only makes easier the process operation, but also increases system speed, eliminates massive paper works, improves the quality of production, minimizes the fatal issue, restricts the unauthorized intervention and saves penalty charges without hampering the process operation through data communication methodology.

The traditional workflow models are based on a procedural, pictorial chart and graph based pattern to enumerate the operating process of a business

process or workflow in a process centric perspective [1].

The data centric business artifact combines both the data and process flow simultaneously in a holistic manner [2].

Firstly, the integrated process management was introduced in the process system whose main objective is to minimize the paper through soft work. The main fields of operation are gate pass entry, bill entry and evaluation, work management, material requisition, work permit issue, vendor registration, material issue, training modules, soft manual & drawing processing, lockout tag out system,

equipment maintenance schedule and safety or fatal issue report logging.

Earlier it was a hectic situation to consider all of the mentioned categories which lead to consumption of huge amount of paper as well as its misplacement may leads to loss of important data in hard copy.

Secondly, as per the updated guidelines of WBSLDC (West Bengal State Load Dispatch Center) each power industry injecting power to the main grid shall declare their injecting schedule prior a day advance in order to control the transmission burden and well as cost losses of the West Bengal government.

Earlier there was no such strict rule regarding the export of power through WBSLDC irrespective of operating line frequency, i.e. 49.7 Hertz for lower range and 50.05 Hertz for higher range, i.e. "49.7 Hz to 50.05 Hz".

The UI (unscheduled injection) charges are applicable to lower frequency with rupees seven per unit, but with the introduction of 7th block sent out MW low/high reversal system, the UI of various power trading parties are under control due to the levy of penalty charges.

Here we have developed a 96 block injection schedule display system for 24 hours calculation, which display the injection data after every fifteen minutes, so that we can get the exact lagging or leading injection to the grid with maintaining the revised frequency, i.e. 49.85 Hertz for lower and 50.05 Hertz for higher range.

In case of and deviation the injection will be accordingly adjusted after sixth block so that unnecessary UI charges get nullified.

One hour (60 minutes) equals to 4 blocks then for 24 hours will be 96 blocks and each block represents either negative or positive injection after every 15 minutes.

Integrated Process System

The IPS (Integrated Process System) is a common workbench by which planning, forecasting, auditing, work permit, billing, material's management etc. can be control effectively through computer and Ethernet network [3].

This system includes a software programming based operating platform that processes the various management work requests.

To run the various applications related to IPS, it needs a high configuring machine with extended memory and hard disk system.

Below Fig 1.0 depicts the simplified overall view of IPS system.

Fig.1.0.Overall view of IPS

This single window multi-icon system contains various vital management activities as follows-

Material Issue & Report Activities

The older material issued system in the industry was done by submitting a material receive note to the store in hard and collect the required material from the store. The disadvantages of such manual system are as follows-

- a. Difficult to predict present stock quantity.
- b. Difficult to locate material location (rack no & row).

- c. Inventory status unknown.
- d. Budget heads difficult to identify.
- e. Need superior signature to issue the material, etc.

The implementation of IPS material issue and report generation system diminished all the above disadvantages by computer-based single window technology, which can be visible to all in the local area network.

The material issue form is so designed that digital signature, budget heat, material location, etc. can be easily seen.

Upon submitting the digital material issue form, it will pop up a window to the store in charge's computer and after granting the issue, you will get a notification to your computer or in mobile to come and collect the material from the store. The below Fig 2.0, depicts the faceplate diagram of material issue.

Fig.2.0.Material issue window

Bill Log Activities

The bill entry activity against any order in the same financial year is done by the accounting department of any organization. Forecasting in financial

accountancy determines the in and out cash-flow of an organization. The following Fig 3.0, will show the bill's approval flow sequence.

Fig.3.0.Material issue window

Bill's log activity through IPS has become a boon for the account and financial persons, and the main advantage is that they can trace the bill easily at any time. The loss or misplace of the bill got minimized and the year to date, bill's forecasting is definitely viewable.

Fig 4.0, shows the detail faceplate view of the bill and report log activity through IPS.

Fig.4.0.Bill Log window

Work Permit Issue Activities

Work permit issue plays a vital role in performing any type of maintenance job. It provides the information about –

- a. Equipment isolation instruction.
- b. Equipment downtime period.
- c. Cross permit detail (if any).
- d. Equipment preventive maintenance frequency.
- e. PPE (personal protective equipment) details.
- f. LOTO (lockout tag out) information
- g. SOP (standard operating procedures) in some cases.
- h. Work information (WI).
- i. Defect description.
- j. Manpower detail.
- k. PTW (Permit to Work) cancellation detail (if any).
- l. Issue authority & receiver signature.
- m. Work type i.e. normal work, hot work, chemical work, height work, evacuation works, etc.

n. Work activity, i.e. PM, O/H (overhauling), repairing, modification, CBM (condition based monitoring), TBM (time based maintenance), AMC (annual rate contract), checking, calibration, lubrication, CAPEX, service support, 2S (industrial cleaning), CLIT (clean lubricate inspect tightness) etc.

o. PTW issue date and time, etc.

The older manual PTW issue process involved many complexities as it has as many as three copies, one of the copies will be retained with control room superintendent, next one to the safety officer in command (LOTO in-charge) and final copy with issuing engineer.

Moreover, it saves paper usage, minimizes the chances of loss or misplacement, single window view to every user, and generates PTW history list etc. The basic faceplate single window view is shown in the below Fig 5.0.

Fig.5.0.Bill Log window

Security System Activities

The security system of any company acts as a safeguard for the man-machine interface. It works like the mitochondria (biological terms, helps in human cellular respiration) of industry to restrict material theft, steal, unauthorized gate entry; mob

gathering, material in and out pass, vehicle kilometer logging, watchdog status report, etc

The simplified single window security activity through the IPS system is depicted in the below Fig 6.0

User Name: User Department: Last Logged In: Logout

GATE IN FORMAT

Name: I* Name: Age:

Visiting Person:

Date: Time: ESI / Medical No:

Company Name: Address:

Tools Entry: No. of days:

Purpose of Visit:

Security Tips and Norms:

Fig.6.0.Security Gate in Log window

HR (Human Resource) activities

As per the definition provided by Sir E.B Flippo, "human-resource management is the planning, organizing, directing and controlling of the procurement, development, resources to the end to the end that the individual & societal basic objectives are fulfilled [4].

The declared objective of HR management is as follows-

- Employee social security and its welfare.
- Proper remuneration.
- Employee motivation.
- An employee works growth by motivation and training.

- 360 degree Employee appraisal program
- Proper utilization of human resources
- Corporate social responsibility.
- Ensuring respect among the employees.
- Third party and vendor management activities.
- Employee conveyance & time management.
- Ensuring employee insurance etc.

In early 1890, the first labor organization was formed and known by the name Bombay mill's hand association for creating a healthy workmen environment and to take care of rightful dues, privileges, and appeals of workers.

The modern human-resource management was started in the late 1920, for smooth work bonding between employee and industry numerous seminars and training were conducted to mark out the various activities with respect to manpower planning, management development, industrial relationship (by labor management department) for maintaining a workable and green culture in the small factories or in a corporate environment.

The overall planning and execution of a human resource and industrial relation department are now merged in a smart way to a single window concept in the soft pattern by network computing, to minimize the overburden of manual writing and reduced the paper consumption by introducing IPS.

A glimpse of HR activities for registration of the vendor application form in the IPS format faceplate is shown in the Fig 7.0,below.

User Name : **User Department:** **Last Logged In:** **Logout**

Inbox :
 Vendor Registration
 Licence Renewal
 Insurance Policy
 Grievance Handling

Outbox :
 Attendance & Leave
 Training Activity
 CSR Activity
 Salary Statements
 Core Value & Policy
 360 degree Appraisal
 Recognition

Vendor Registration

Vendor Name : PAN No. :

Type : No of Employee :

Date : Time : Work Profile :

Address : Phone No :

TIN : ITR Detail : Current A/C detail :

Vendor Detail :

EDIT **SUBMIT** **PRINT**

Fig.7.0.Vendor registration format

Safety Activities

Occupational health and safety define that the conditions and the factors that can harm the health of any employee and worker across the workplace and can be treated as the most prior and emergency case in all respect.

Various rules and norms are designated as per the ISO (International Organization for Standardization) which covers at least few of the below-mentioned points-

- a) Hazard identification & Risk assessment.
- b) Plan Do Check Act (PDCA).
- c) Safety policies & SOPs (Standard Operating Procedures).
- d) Environmental Aspects & its impacts.
- e) HAZOP & LOTO System.
- f) Safety Planning & its implementation.
- g) Records, documentation & trainings.
- h) Evaluation of compliance.
- i) Nonconformity against violation.

- j) Corrective & preventive measures.
- k) Internal audit.
- l) Legal compliance record.
- m) Management review & communication etc.

The two factors in significance screening can be able to determine the cause and signs of risk assessment are severity and likelihood.

Severity in case of death is assigned as 5.

Major injury assigned as 4.

Illness assigned as 3.

Minor Injury assigned as 2.

Delay as 1.

Likelihood in case of certain to happen is assigned as 5.

Very likely as 4.

Likely as 3.

Unlikely as 2.

Very unlikely as 1.

User Name: **User Department:** **Last Logged In:** **Logout**

Inbox :
 ISO 9001:2015
 ISO 18001:2007
 ISO 14001:2004
 HIRA
 PDCA

Outbox :
 Safety Policies
 Safety Slogans
 Safety Aspects
 Safety SOP's
 EHS Regulation
 IS & H Legislation

HIRA Hazard Identification & Risk Assessment Format

Activity : Hazard :

Hazard Type : Risk :

Severity : Likelihood : Future Precaution :

Equipment / System : Risk Rating :

Date : Time : Emergency Contact No :

Detail of affected person/Person at Risk :

EDIT **SUBMIT** **PRINT**

Fig.8.0 HIRA generalized window

7th Block Sent Out MW Low/High Reversal System

New salient features of new DSM (deviation settlement mechanism) 2018.

- i. The change of frequency band in for DSM price vector.
- ii. Clubbing of DSM price vector with ACP (Average Clearing Price).
- iii. New capping rates for generating stations.
- iv. One directional deviation from schedule causes sustained penalty.

Extra charges for over injection or under drawl for frequency 50.05Hz and above.

Earlier injection system the penalties are only due to UI in case of lower frequencies (49.7 Hz) which arises the following cases.

Let a power trading company (PTC) planned a schedule injection of 100 MW on tomorrow for 24 hours.

Case 1. If PTC exports power 100.55 MW in 24 hours keeping frequency within range, then no penalty will be charged.

Case 2. If PTC exports power 100.55 MW in 24 hours but frequency is below 49.7 Hz, then a penalty of Rs 6 per unit multiplied by number of hours will be charged.

Case 3. If PTC exports power 99.05 MW in 24 keeping frequency within range, then no penalty will be charged.

Case 4. If PTC exports power 99.05 MW in 24 hours but frequency is below 49.7 Hz, then a penalty of Rs 6 per unit multiplied by number of hours will be charged.

As per WBSLDC new rule regarding the power injection to the grid, the PTC must declare their schedule

injection one day prior and revision shall be applicable on the same day latest by 10.00 pm. The penalty charge of reschedule will be Rs. 10,000 in case of time taking breakdown while injection is in process.

The concept of 7th block sent out MW low/high reversal steps are as follow.

- a. PTC has to declare their schedule injection.
- b. Your 24 hours sent out will be divided into 96 blocks of 15 minutes duration.
- c. The line frequency shall be maintained within 49.85 Hz for lower range & 50.05 Hz for higher range.

d. If PTC unable to keep the required MW injection per block of 15 minutes up to 6th block, then PTC has to inject a higher or lower MW than desired MW on the 7th block, failing which will penalized as previous day average UI charge with 20% per unit cost.

e. If PTC unable to keep the required MW injection per block of 15 minutes up to 11th block, then PTC has to inject a higher or lower MW than desired MW on the 12th block, failing which will penalized as previous day average UI charge with 40% per unit cost.

f. If PTC unable to keep the required MW injection per block of 15 minutes up to 17th block, then PTC has to inject a higher or lower MW than desired MW on the 18th block, failing which will penalized as previous day average UI charge with 100% per unit cost.

g. A cost of Rs.3 per unit will be panelized with above points (d, e and f) if frequency is below the lower range, i.e. 49.7Hz

h. A cost of Rs.8 per unit will be panelized with above points (d, e and f) if frequency is above the higher range, i.e. 50.05Hz

The below Fig. 9.0 depicts the overview of 96 block MW sent out display status for 24 hours ("00:00 hours to 23:59:59 hours").

Fig.9.0 Overview of 96 blocks MW sent out

The outputs of the sent out megawatt is taken from the output of tri-vector meter of line 1 and line 2 and helps in building the logic. A faceplate of the above said quote is shown in the below Fig. 10.0.

Fig.10.0 Faceplate of outgoing MW

The DSM price vector difference of WBSLDC show on below Table 1, the NLDC (National Load Dispatch Center) will declare the daily DSM rates.

TABLE 1
Differences in old and new DSM rates

OLD DSM RATES		4TH AMENDMENT DSM RATES	
Frequency (Hz)	Deviation (Paisa/Kwh)	Frequency (Hz)	Deviation (Paisa/Kwh)
50.05	0	50.05	0

OLD DSM RATES		4TH AMENDMENT DSM RATES	
Frequency (Hz)	Deviation (Paisa/Kwh)	Frequency (Hz)	Deviation (Paisa/Kwh)
50.00	178	50.04 to 50.01	Price as per slope at frequency within 50.05Hz
49.94	303.08	50.00	Daily average ACP
49.70	803.20	49.99 to 49.85	Price as per slope at frequency within 50.05Hz
Under 49.70	824.04	Under 49.85	800

Mathematical Demonstration Of Ui Penalty Criteria

How much penalty it will cost if any PTC (Power Trading Company) scheduled a 42 MW and the line frequency is below 49.85 Hz?

Let us suppose the 15 min duration of six consecutive blocks, represents as

As the MW injection on block 1, 3 & 5 is higher than the required so it is mandate to inject MW below 7.0 on the 7th block, else a penalty of previous day Ui (Unscheduled Injection) charge + Rs. 3 per unit/Block will be applicable.

$$\text{Injected MW} = 7.1 + 7.0 + 7.2 + 7.0 + 7.1 + 7.0 = 42.3 \text{ MW}$$

$$\text{Schedule injection} = 42 \text{ MW}$$

Extra injection with low frequency = $42.3 - 42$

= $0.3 \text{ MW} = 300 \text{ KW}$ ($\therefore 1 \text{ MW} = 1000 \text{ KW}$)

Suppose the previous day UI penalty charge was Rs. 2000 and the injection got lower on 9th block.

$\therefore$ Actual Penalty = $2000 + (300 \times 3 \times 9)$

= Rs. 10100 is the actual penalty charge

Thus, the PTC has to give a penalty of Rs 10,100 to WBSLDC.

Similarly, a penalty of Rs. 8 per unit/block will be applicable if the frequency is above 50.05Hz.

Conclusion

Earlier type of manual data interpretation in hard format for work flow and penalties due to unscheduled injection was bulky process centric system which is now normalized by proper data centric business artifacts. The IPS and 7th block sent out MW system is in soft for easier monitor, manage, modify and control of plant process leads to service excellence.

Each workflow mentioned can be a useful web service with its monopolistic data model and all the information required to build the model is based on its uniqueness of work flow technique [5].

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